

ANOMALOUS INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING SENSITIVE H-BOND STRUCTURE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

BY HEMLATA KAZI AND C. M. DESAI

Interfacial tension measurements of liquids, such as amylⁱ acetate or butylⁿ acetate, having unstable H-bond structure, against aqueous sodium oleate, cadmium iodide, mixtures of cadmium and potassium iodides, mixtures of acid and base, and mixtures of potassium chromate and lead nitrate show maxima or minima at certain electrolyte concentrations; while benzene and hexane, not having such a structure, do not indicate such a behaviour.

The interfacial tension-concentration curves of aqueous sodium or potassium oleate with hexyl or octyl alcohols, butyl or amyl acetates, show a sharp minimum at extreme dilution, followed by a maximum far above the tension value for pure water, and then the usual decrease in tension with further increase in soap concentration (Kazi and Desai, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 218; this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 209, 283). With salts showing autocomplexing, such as cadmium iodide, this maximum is followed by a minimum and then again a maximum (*ibid.*, 1954, 31, 418, 636). Different number of peaks have been observed with different salt systems (*ibid.*, 1954, 31, 163, 957; 1955, 32, 63; 1956, 33, 513). Liquids such as hexane and benzene, not having such H-bond structure, do not show such a behaviour (cf. Heintz and Hume, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 462). The typical behaviour has been explained on the basis of the reversal of the electrical double layer at the liquid-water interface with change in ionic character, the liquid having a sensitive H-bond structure (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 769). It has been now noticed that the interfacial tension measurements of liquids, such as amylⁱ acetate and butylⁿ acetate, indicate a sharp minimum at the equivalence point, when a base is added to an acid or an electrolyte is added to another forming a sparingly soluble salt; while hexane and benzene do not show such behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this work the interfacial tension measurements of amylⁱ acetate or butylⁿ acetate, benzene and hexane against aqueous cadmium iodide, sodium oleate, mixtures of cadmium and potassium iodides, mixtures of potassium chromate and lead nitrate and mixtures of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid have been made with all details at varying concentrations. The aqueous mixtures were prepared by the monovariation method. The sparingly soluble lead chromate was filtered off and the clear filtrate was used for the tension measurements. The Burrows and Welcome micro-syringe (capacity 1.0 c.c., capillary radius 0.05 cm, tip radius 0.139 cm), which registers the volume of a single drop with an accuracy of 0.0004 c.c., was used for the purpose. The syringe with liquid phase was clamped vertically with its tip pointing upward, the barrel being fitted in the container, holding aqueous solution, by means of a tightly

fitting rubber bung. The substances used were of A.R. quality. The esters were treated with sodium carbonate solution, washed with water, dried and distilled. The middle fractions were used for the purpose.

Drop Weight Volume Method for the Interfacial Tension Measurements.—The edge of the liquid phase was brought exactly to the end of the capillary at the tip by the movement of the micrometer screw head and the reading on the scale was noted. Each drop of the liquid was allowed to be formed and released very slowly in the aqueous phase by the gradual motion of the screw head; the reading on the scale was again noted and from the volume, thus obtained, the interfacial tension was calculated by the equation :

$$\gamma = \frac{v(d-d')g}{2\pi r \frac{r}{v^{\frac{1}{2}}}} = \frac{v(d-d')g\phi}{2\pi r}$$

The densities, measured and used for calculations, were those of the mutual phases; the consecutive density variations are so small that they hardly make significant difference in the third or fourth decimal place of the tension values. The corrections involved are the same as those of drop weight method (W. D. Harkins, "Physical Chemistry of Surface Films". Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1952). The literature values for interfacial tensions of pure benzene, hexane, amyl acetate and butyl acetate against pure water are 34.1, 49.7, 12.09 and 14.9 dynes cm^{-1} respectively. The details as regards electrolyte concentrations, corresponding volumes of a single drop of the liquids and the corresponding tension values are recorded in Tables I-V.

TABLE I

Conc. of CdI_2 ($M \times 10^3$).	Volume of one drop (in c.c.).			Interfacial surface tension (dynes/cm).		
	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyli acetate.	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyli acetate.
0.00	0.1776	0.0948	0.0552	33.59	49.69	12.04
0.05	0.2068	0.0896	0.0540	38.41	47.49	11.83
0.075	0.2168	0.0884	0.0576	40.11	46.86	12.50
0.10	0.2084	0.0876	0.0612	38.70	46.46	13.30
0.25	0.2020	0.0848	0.0640	37.65	45.01	13.93
0.50	0.1964	0.0836	0.0692	37.27	44.46	14.91
1.00	0.1768	0.0828	0.0608	33.44	44.07	13.23
2.50	0.1720	0.0806	0.0556	32.56	43.12	12.20
4.00	0.1700	0.0784	0.0544	32.20	41.88	11.89
6.00	0.1624	0.0764	0.0600	30.84	40.84	13.09
7.00	0.1532	0.0752	0.0640	29.19	40.20	13.93
9.00	0.1472	0.0744	0.0588	28.09	39.86	12.83
15.00	0.1420	0.0740	0.0524	27.18	39.64	11.52
30.00	0.1308	0.0724	0.0468	25.14	38.24	10.39

TABLE II

Conc. Na-oleate ($M \times 10^3$).	Volume of one drop (in c.c.).			Interfacial surface tension (dynes/cm).		
	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ⁱ acetate.	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ⁱ acetate.
0.00	0.1776	0.0948	0.0552	33.59	49.69	12.04
0.025	0.1764	0.0900	0.0536	33.36	47.76	11.76
0.05	0.1736	0.0848	0.0516	32.86	45.10	11.30
0.075	0.1700	0.0828	0.0524	32.20	44.11	11.52
0.10	0.1680	0.0812	0.0572	31.87	43.29	12.48
0.25	0.1560	0.0788	0.0592	29.70	42.04	12.90
0.50	0.1480	0.0676	0.0612	28.25	36.55	13.32
1.00	0.1228	0.0564	0.0572	23.82	30.86	12.48
2.00	0.0988	0.0484	0.0508	19.41	26.57	11.18
3.00	0.0716	0.0296	0.0440	13.71	16.99	9.75
5.00	0.0458	0.0216	0.0392	10.11	12.68	8.73
8.00	0.0428	0.0168	0.0324	8.94	10.07	7.16
10.00	0.0388	0.0144	0.0284	8.18	8.73	6.55
30.00	0.0312	0.0104	0.0204	6.22	6.40	4.80

TABLE III

$M/100$ -CdI ₂ added to 24 c.c. of $M/100$ -KI + H ₂ O to 100 c.c.	Volume of one drop (in c.c.).			Interfacial surface tension (dynes/cm).		
	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ⁱ acetate.	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ⁱ acetate.
0.00 c.c.	0.1712	0.0984	0.0616	32.41	51.58	13.37
4.0	0.1632	0.0952	0.0672	30.98	49.94	14.21
8.0	0.1564	0.0928	0.0728	29.78	49.00	15.64
10.0	0.1548	0.0912	0.0744	29.44	48.23	15.90
12.0	0.1488	0.0904	0.0756	28.38	47.92	16.10
14.0	0.1480	0.0900	0.0728	28.25	47.76	15.64
16.0	0.1468	0.0892	0.0680	28.03	47.35	14.63
20.0	0.1428	0.0856	0.0732	27.34	45.51	15.72
22.0	0.1420	0.0844	0.0740	27.20	44.88	15.89
24.0	0.1404	0.0828	0.0768	26.96	44.11	16.47
28.0	0.1392	0.0804	0.0700	26.75	42.89	15.11
32.0	0.1376	0.0780	0.0644	26.43	41.61	13.96
36.0	0.1352	0.0752	0.0544	25.98	40.23	11.92
42.0	0.1324	0.0724	0.0480	25.48	38.84	10.61
48.0	0.1316	0.0648	0.0464	25.34	36.91	10.27

TABLE IV

<i>M</i> /10-K ₂ CrO ₄ added to 10 c.c. of <i>M</i> /10-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + H ₂ O to 100 c.c.	Volume of one drop (in c.c.).			Interfacial surface tension (dynes/cm).		
	Benzene.	Hexane	Butyl ¹ acetate.	Benzene.	Hexane.	Butyl ¹ acetate.
0.00 c.c.	0.1732	0.0916	0.0424	32.78	48.42	8.72
2.0	0.1672	0.0872	0.0380	31.74	46.28	7.88
4.0	0.1624	0.0856	0.0352	30.85	45.53	7.36
6.0	0.1592	0.0828	0.0340	30.40	44.11	7.11
8.0	0.1516	0.0812	0.0324	28.92	43.29	6.81
9.5	0.1484	0.0788	0.0284	28.32	42.04	6.01
9.9	0.1460	0.0776	0.0272	27.91	41.40	5.79
10.0	0.1416	0.0768	0.0324	27.05	41.03	6.81
10.1	0.1400	0.0748	0.0364	26.87	40.01	7.60
10.5	0.1380	0.0740	0.0404	26.52	39.64	8.35
12.0	0.1372	0.0684	0.0449	26.36	36.91	9.17
15.0	0.1284	0.0672	0.0492	24.77	36.34	10.03
17.0	0.1256	0.0672	0.0508	24.31	36.34	10.34
20.0	0.1176	0.0652	0.0544	22.84	35.42	10.98

TABLE V

<i>N</i> /10-NaOH added to 10 c.c. of <i>N</i> /10-HCl + H ₂ O to 100 c.c.	Volume of one drop (in c.c.).			Interfacial surface tension (dynes/cm).		
	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ¹ acetate.	Benzene.	Hexane.	Amyl ¹ acetate.
0.0 c.c.	0.1828	0.0908	0.0640	34.39	48.0	13.89
2.0	0.1612	0.0812	0.0615	30.63	43.29	13.33
5.0	0.1520	0.0744	0.0572	28.98	39.86	12.48
7.0	0.1476	0.0712	0.0552	28.18	38.26	12.09
9.5	0.1384	0.0655	0.0488	26.56	35.62	10.76
9.9	0.1376	0.0648	0.0476	26.43	35.26	10.53
10.0	0.1340	0.0644	0.0448	25.74	35.12	9.92
10.1	0.1328	0.0632	0.0528	25.54	34.51	11.60
10.5	0.1312	0.0624	0.0616	25.26	34.13	13.44
12.0	0.1092	0.0608	0.0648	21.32	33.32	14.09
20.0	0.1044	0.0572	0.0700	20.49	31.46	15.11

DISCUSSION

The drop volume or tension measurements of amyl¹ acetate against aqueous cadmium iodide indicate two peaks at $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $7.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ salt concentrations; while benzene and hexane do not show these peaks (Table I). With aqueous sodium oleate, the ester shows a peak at $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$, preceded by a minimum at $0.05 \times 10^{-3}M$; whereas benzene and hexane show a decrease in tension with increasing soap concentrations (Table II). At two stoichiometric compositions of cadmium and potassium iodides (1:2 and 1:1) two maxima are observed with the ester, whereas benzene and hexane show decreasing tensions with increasing concentrations (Table III). With increasing addition of potassium chromate to lead nitrate solution, the tension of the

ester goes on decreasing till a minimum is reached at the equivalence point, and then it rises with the addition of the chromate (Table IV). The addition of the base to the acid shows the same typical behaviour (Table V). In both these cases benzene and hexane do not indicate such minimum values at the equivalence point. It is interesting to note that the conclusions drawn from the drop volume results are in complete agreement with those from the corresponding tension data; hence it should not be imperative in future work along these lines to calculate tension values.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M.T.B. COLLEGE, SURAT.

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